

Business Service Identification: A Review of Methods and Techniques

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Abstract: The business service paradigm offers a set of design concerns to aid organizations in creating service architectures to define and manage their services. To utilize the paradigm in an organizational setting, scholars have proposed operational procedures called service identification methods and techniques. However, there is a misalignment between the design concerns associated with business services, and the design concerns the service identification methods and techniques address. Recognizing this issue, this study investigates service identification methods and techniques by means of a systematic literature review to increase the understanding of the extent to which methods and techniques address the design concerns.

Keywords: Business service, Service identification, Service identification method, Service architecture, Systematic literature review

1 Introduction

The effects of digitization, advancements in information technology, and the emergence of a multitude of delivery channels have blurred the lines of markets and created a global economy (Engel and Ebel, 2019). Now, more than ever, organizations are facing competition from traditional and non-traditional players and a plethora of regulatory and governmental compliance requirements (Cherbakov *et al.*, 2005; Turetken *et al.*, 2012; Turetken *et al.*, 2012; Elgammal *et al.*, 2016). Simultaneously, the abundance of offerings from various sources in shared market spaces has led to high and volatile customer expectations (Tripsas, 2008). The culmination of these factors has created demands for innovation, flexibility, and shorter time to market for novel offerings, and a constant desire to create new revenue sources (Kowalkowski, 2011).

In response, organizations have begun to shift their attention away from transactional product sales to relational services and solutions to better cater to the needs of their customers and their relationships within their business networks (Gummesson, Lusch and Vargo, 2010; Ostrom *et al.*, 2010; Grefen and Turetken, 2018). They are increasingly undertaking initiatives to (re-)configure their diverse resources, such as people, skills, processes, technology, and information (Wetter-Edman *et al.*, 2014) to develop compelling value propositions and to innovate complex service systems with others (Vargo, Maglio and Akaka, 2008; Briscoe, Keränen and Parry, 2012; Böhmman, Leimeister and Möslin, 2014; Ostrom *et al.*, 2015). Thus, as modern organizations are increasingly aiming at providing comprehensive and complex services (Böttcher and Klingner, 2011; Turetken and Grefen, 2017; Mastrogiacomo, Barravecchia and Franceschini, 2018), the increasing complexity concerning the composition and management of the resource configurations becomes a major challenge in service provisioning (Ostrom *et al.*, 2015).

One key concept to address this challenge is service architecture (Heiskala, Tiihonen and Soininen, 2005; Voss and Hsuan, 2009; Estrada *et al.*, 2013; Böhmman, Leimeister and Möslin, 2014, 2014; Beverungen, Lüttenberg and Wolf, 2018) - the scheme by which a complex service system is decomposed into functional elements that encapsulate complex configurations of resources (Voss and Hsuan, 2009; Böhmman, Leimeister and Möslin, 2014). The design, representation, creation, and analysis of the functional elements of service architectures are addressed within the *business services paradigm* (Cherbakov *et al.*, 2005; Sanz and Becker, 2006; Nayak *et al.*, 2007). The paradigm builds on the application of service-oriented computing approaches and the principles of service-oriented architecture (SOA) - to collaborative business environments such as service systems (Cherbakov *et al.*, 2005; Zhao, Tanniru and Zhang, 2007; Demirkan *et al.*, 2008). As such, it is based on the idea of elevating the service abstraction from the information

technology/software level to the business level for creating detailed models of the functional elements required for achieving business goals (Estrada *et al.*, 2010; Plugge and Janssen, 2019). To realize this idea, the paradigm conceptualizes *business service* as an architectural construct to model the functional elements of a service architecture (Flaxer and Nigam, 2004; Sanz and Becker, 2006; Estrada *et al.*, 2013) and *business service identification* (Hakanen and Jaakkola, 2012) as the process of modeling and defining the functional elements of service architecture by employing the business service construct. Business service identification is guided by *design concerns* (Adali *et al.*, 2021), each addressing a specific service management challenge, such as establishing the alignment between the service offerings and the long-term strategic interests of the organization (Arsanjani *et al.*, 2008) or achieving standardization, modularity, and specialization in service offerings (Sanz, Nayak and Becker, 2006).

The literature offers a multitude of *service identification methods (SIMs)*, each proposing a technique to identify business services while addressing a number of design concerns. Such a technique focuses on a key business artifact (e.g., a business process, business goal, business function, or feature) and includes a set of activities that employ this artifact in the business service identification (Gu and Lago, 2010). The literature also includes secondary studies that identify a wide array of design concerns and investigate SIMs from various perspectives, each emphasizing a subset of such design concerns (Birkmeier, Klöckner and Overhage, 2009; Gu and Lago, 2010; Cai, Liu and Wang, 2011; Vale *et al.*, 2012; Huergo *et al.*, 2014). The varying nature of design concerns addressed in each SIM raises investigative concerns about their comparability, consistency, and differences (Adali *et al.*, 2020). This complexity makes it challenging to discern the specific functionalities of each SIM and to determine the optimal circumstances for their use. This reduces the utility of the SIMs for the service architects and designers. Thus, there is a need for an investigation that provides an overview and a synthesis of the design concerns and a clarification of how well these design concerns are addressed by SIMs.

Targeting this need, we present a study of two systematic literature reviews (SLRs) that focus on the design concerns associated with business services (SLR-1) and SIMs that focus on the identification of *business services* (SLR-2). As such, the research objective of SLR-1 is the *identification and synthesis of the design concerns associated with the business service concept*, and the research objective of SLR-2 is *the investigation of the extent to which existing service identification methods address the design concerns related to “business services”, and how (by which techniques) they address these concerns*.

To address these objectives, we formulated a set of research questions, searched relevant studies published between the years 2000 and 2021 (June) in established electronic libraries, and identified the design concerns associated with business services and reported SIMs. In total, we analyzed 16 studies proposing 10 design concerns associated with business services, along with 47 SIMs and 13 techniques for business service identification. Furthermore, we thoroughly studied the extent to which each technique -and consequently each SIM- addresses the *design concerns*. The results of our analysis provide a synthesis of the design concerns that guide business service identification and detailed information on the extent to which these techniques and SIMs address the concerns and how they can be improved. Finally, our study provides an overview of the state-of-the-art research on business service identification and guidance to practitioners in selecting the most suitable SIMs for creating service architectures to manage the complexity of their service offerings.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we discuss other SLR studies conducted on SIMs and clarify the significance of our study with respect to its scope and focus. In Section 3, we introduce our research design, including the review procedures for locating relevant studies and the data models for the extraction of the items for the analysis of the studies. In Section 4, we present the findings and results of our study. In Section 5, we discuss our findings. Finally, in Section 6, we provide the conclusions and implications for research and practice and discuss the limitations of our study along with future research directions.

2 Related Work

In this section, we present and discuss secondary studies that have been performed on SIMs. Table 1 presents an overview of such studies, including also how our work compares to them.

Table 1: An Overview of the SLRs Conducted on SIMs

Authors	Year	Summary	Sources Covered	Years Covered	Number of Methods Analysed
Gu & Lago	2010	Focuses on the categorization of basic elements of SIMs for service-oriented architecture (SOA) to aid practitioners in selecting the most appropriate one.	ACM, IEEEExplore, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink	2004 - 2009	30
Huergo et al.	2014	Analyses SIMs based on a classification scheme mainly derived from a SOA reference architecture	ACM, IEEEExplore, DBLP Scopus	2002 - 2013 (June)	105
Bani-Ismael & Baghdadi	2018	Explores challenges of service identification in SOA by analysing the challenges claimed by previous work.	Scopus	2005 - 2016	Not Applicable
This SLR	2021	Investigates SIMs focusing on the identification of <i>business</i> services with a holistic perspective on the conceptualization of business services as proposed by the literature	Ebsco, ScienceDirect, Scopus SpringerLink, Web of Science, and Wiley	2000 – 2021 (June)	47

In their review, Gu and Lago (2010) classify and compare 30 SIMs. They analyze these SIMs with respect to the types of business artifacts that they take as input, the outputs they generate, and the techniques they apply for identifying the services. The main contribution of their work is an input-output matrix, which is proposed to help practitioners compare the identified techniques and select them based on available resources and identified needs.

Huergo et al. (2014) extended Gu and Lago’s study with a significant number of additional SIMs. They use the OASIS reference architecture (OASIS, 2006) designed for SOA to compare and evaluate 105 SIMs that they selected. Their classification scheme includes 10 perspectives: participant concerns, the context of transactions, service value to the business, service description, behavior model detailing, information model detailing, service granularity, service dependency, type of conversation, and quality attributes elicitation. Overall, they evaluate and compare 105 SIMs by examining their alignment with these perspectives.

Bani-Ismael and Baghdadi (2018) do not explicitly focus on SIMs but investigate the challenges in service identification. In their work, they report 8 challenges: service quality attributes (QAs), service granularity, business-IT alignment, tool support, validation, systematic SIM, comprehensive SIM, input artifact, and configurability of SIM. The latter 4 focus on SIMs.

Although all 3 review studies aim to provide a comprehensive analysis of service identification, they approach the topic through an IT-dominant lens. Through this lens, business service identification space is limited to software functionality encapsulated in software components that are accessible via technical interfaces (e.g., web services). In this regard, Gu and Lago define service identification as the “determination of services that are appropriate for use in an SOA”. However, as future work, they address the need for a differentiation between services focusing on value creation and services for internal consumption. Likewise, Huergo et al. (2014) evaluate SIMs with an evaluation scheme derived from an SOA reference architecture. Although their evaluation scheme includes *business concerns*, it misses the service provisioning and, thus, the business service design concerns, such as the linking value propositions or processes that enable the provision of business services. This issue is also present in the work by Bani-Ismael and Baghdadi, as they explicitly focus on challenges in the scope of SOA. This IT-dominant perspective is criticized by researchers for being “incomplete and unnecessarily limiting” due to its disregard for the value co-creating services (Akkermans, Baida and Gordijn, 2004).

Recognizing this, we approach service identification from a holistic perspective and focus on the service offerings of an organization without distinguishing their type or favoring one type of service over another. We aim to achieve this with an explicit focus on *business services* which in turn distinguishes our work from existing literature reviews. While previous reviews also include valuable discussion on the identification of business services, they do not fully investigate the *design concerns* associated with them. To focus on business services, this SLR analyses SIMs with a data extraction model (see Section 3.2.3) built upon the design concerns as discussed in the literature.

3 Research Design and Execution

In this section, we first present our research questions. Next, we describe the design and execution of the systematic reviews with the details of the protocol we followed to answer our research questions.

3.1 Research Questions

Guided by our research objective, we have formulated four research questions (RQs). The literature provides different conceptualizations of the term business service. Each conceptualization caters to a set of *design concerns* intrinsic to the context in which the term is used. Therefore, the investigation of the extent to which design concerns are addressed by SIMs should be preceded by an exploration of the design concerns associated with business services first and then SIMs. Therefore, our first and second research questions, respectively, relate to the identification of the reported design concerns and SIMs in the academic literature:

RQ-1. What design concerns have been associated with the business service concept in the academic literature?

RQ-2. What SIMs have been proposed in the academic literature?

Whether a SIM addresses a design concern can be determined by checking the technique or the combination of techniques that the SIM applies to address that design concern. As discussed in Hubbers et al. (2007) and Gu & Lago (2010), these identification techniques are the procedures that SIMs follow/employ to identify business services. Thus, they dictate the perspective that SIMs adopt, and hence, the design concerns they address within their scope, as well as those they leave behind. Therefore, our third research question relates to the exploration of the service identification techniques that SIMs follow:

RQ-3. What service identification techniques do the proposed SIMs follow?

Each service identification technique addresses one or more design concerns to a certain extent. Therefore, our fourth and final question relates to the discovery of the design concerns that each service identification technique and, consequently, the SIMs address, and how (by which techniques) these concerns are addressed:

RQ-4. To what extent do the service identification techniques and, consequently, the SIMs address the business service design concerns?

3.2 Design and Execution of the Systematic Literature Reviews

While our research questions all relate to business service identification, answering our explorative research questions RQ-1 and RQ-2 require the design of different search protocols. Therefore, our study comprises two connected systematic literature reviews, namely *SLR-1* and *SLR-2*, that address different RQs. Accordingly,

SLR-1 addresses RQ-1 by focusing on the business service concept and the design concerns associated with it

SLR-2 addresses RQ-2, 3 & 4 by focusing on SIMs.

Overall, both SLRs follow the guidelines for performing SLRs by Kitchenham and Charters (2007) up to and including Step 4, as shown in Figure 1. However, while *SLR-1* uses a *snowballing technique* for locating relevant studies, *SLR-2* continues following the guidelines of Kitchenham and Charters. In the following

paragraph, we first introduce the steps that are shared between SLR-1 & 2 (Steps 1 through 4 in Figure 1). Then, per SLR, we elaborate on the protocols for locating the relevant studies.

Figure 1: The protocols for the SLR-1 and SLR-2

3.2.1 The Shared Steps of SLR-1 and SLR-2

The first four steps of the SLR-1 and SLR-2 were shared. In Step 1, we defined the research objective and the related research question as described in the introduction section of this paper. In Step 2, we conducted several pilot searches as a preparation phase for the initial search. These searches enabled us to refine the scope, define the search terms, and get a quick overview of the state-of-the-art research in this field to effectively define the criteria to be used to include or exclude a specific study. For our search string, we omitted the additional keywords and decided to use the unrestricting search term “business service” (quotation marks included) for the retrieval of the studies. In Step 3, we selected the following established digital libraries (in alphabetical order) for our search: Ebsco (<https://www.ebsco.com>), ScienceDirect (<https://www.sciencedirect.com>), Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>), SpringerLink (<https://link.springer.com>), Web of Science (<http://apps.webofknowledge.com>), and Wiley (<https://www.wiley.com>). These libraries together cover a broad range of relevant accessible publishers. In Step 4, we conducted the initial search that feeds each SLR by applying the search string to each digital

library's search engine. After Step 4, we followed the protocols we chose for each SLR as described in the following.

3.2.2 Steps of SLR-1

The term business service is used in many different research streams and domains. In our pilot database searches with the search string “business service”, we observed that the majority of the query results returned papers that originated from marketing research. In contrast to IS research, where business services represent architectural entities, marketing research considers them as services exchanged between organizations (i.e., business-to-business services) (Lam *et al.*, 2004). Since the majority of the studies that returned subscribed to the marketing domain and hence were not relevant to our study, locating relevant studies required a comprehensive filtering approach based on the research domain of the studies. However, filtering not only eliminated irrelevant studies but also the relevant interdisciplinary studies that subscribe to multiple domains. Recognizing this, we decided to use a protocol based on the *snowballing technique* to locate relevant studies. Snowballing refers to locating relevant studies by using the reference list of a set of relevant studies (i.e., starting set) along with the citations to the studies in the starting set (Wohlin *et al.*, 2013). As such, this allowed us to control the alignment between the conceptualization of business services in the starting set and conceptualizations in the studies to be located. To ensure the rigor of our review, we adhered to the guidelines for backward and forward snowballing presented in (Wohlin, 2014). An overview of how we applied the guidelines to our search context is presented on the left side of Figure 1.

In Step 5.1, we first, defined and iteratively revised inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 2) for SLR-1 based on our research objective and RQ1.

Table 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for SLR-1

Type of Criterion	ID	Description
Inclusion	IC-1	The study is published between 1-1-2000 and 1-6-2021.
Inclusion	IC-2	The study proposes a conceptualization for business services (e.g., a textual definition, an ontology, or a conceptual model).
Exclusion	EC-1	The study is not publicly available in its complete form.
Exclusion	EC-2	The study is not written in English, which is the most common language in scientific papers.
Exclusion	EC-3	The study is concerned with a service perspective that is not on the business level (i.e., services in the context of information technology (e.g., IT services) and computer science (e.g., web services, e-services).)
Exclusion	EC-4	The study is referring to a business service conceptualization originally published in another study.

Since the early works on the business services (Sanz, Nayak and Becker, 2006) date back to the 2000s, we selected the year 2000 as the start of our inclusion period (IC-1). Since the research objective of SLR-1 is to identify and clarify the design concerns associated with business services, we selected the studies that propose an explicit and unique conceptualization for the term business service (IC-2 and EC-4). Additionally, we adopted a holistic perspective and did not distinguish between different types of services, as long as they relate to the service offerings of an organization. Accordingly, we excluded papers that focus on services exclusively in the context of information technology (e.g., IT services) and computer science (e.g., web services, e-services). This is reflected in our EC-3. Finally, EC-1 and 2 relate to the studies not being publicly available and written in a language other than English.

After creating the inclusion and exclusion criteria, we sorted the studies identified in Step 4 by their relevance to our search string and applied first IC-1 and then IC-2 on the title, abstract, and keywords of the studies. Since the number of studies returned was too large (>1000), we used cut-off and threshold points in our relevancy scan. Accordingly, the rank of the latest relevant study becomes the cut-off point, and the relevancy scan stops when there are no relevant studies found in the next 150 studies after the cut-off point. This resulted in the selection of 52 studies. After that, we applied IC-2 and EC-1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively, on the full text of the 52 papers. This resulted in the selection of 8 studies for our starting set. The list of the studies in our starting set is given in Appendix A.

After the creation of the starting set, in Steps 6.1 and 7.1, we conducted two iterations, each including a forward and a backward snowballing technique (Wohlin, 2014). Backward snowballing relates to using the reference list of the papers being examined to identify new papers to be included. Forward snowballing relates to examining studies to identify new studies citing the studies being examined. Table 3 presents an overview of the number of citations examined and the number of studies selected in each iteration.

Table 3: An Overview of the Number of Citations Examined and Studies Selected in Iterations

Iteration	Backward		Forward	
	# References Examined	# Studies Selected	# Citations Examined	# Studies Selected
Iteration 1	134 (38 duplicates)	2	598 (127 duplicates)	6
Iteration 2	72 (7 duplicates)	0	21 (1 duplicate)	0

In *iteration 1*, we conducted backward and forward snowballing separately on the starting set of eight studies. These studies, in total, had 134 references and 598 citations to them. After the elimination of duplicates from the set of references and citations, we applied our inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 2). In total, iteration 1 resulted in the addition of six studies into the starting set of eight papers.

In *iteration 2*, we conducted backward and forward snowballing on the set of eight additional studies selected in Iteration 1. In total, these studies had 72 references and 21 citations to them. After the removal of the duplicates, we applied our inclusion and exclusion criteria. Iteration 2 resulted in the selection of no studies. Hence, we did not perform another iteration. At the end of both iterations, we reached a final list of 16 studies proposing 16 original conceptualizations of the term business service.

In Step 8.1, we applied *thematic synthesis* to extract and synthesize data from the selected studies (Cruzes and Dyba, 2011a). Our main aim for using this approach was to identify, interpret, and report recurring themes within studies to derive a synthesis of business service design concerns. Accordingly, we followed the steps shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4: Steps of thematic synthesis, taken from studies (Cruzes and Dyba, 2011a)

#	Thematic Synthesis Step	Descriptions
8.1.1	Extract data	Extract data from the primary studies, including bibliographical information, aims, context, and results.
8.1.2	Code data	Identify and code interesting concepts, categories, findings, and results in a systematic fashion across the entire data set.
8.1.3	Translate codes into themes	Translate codes into themes, sub-themes, and higher-order themes.
8.1.4	Create a model of higher-order themes	Explore relationships between themes and create a model of higher-order themes.
8.1.5	Assess the trustworthiness of the synthesis	Assess the trustworthiness of the interpretations leading up to the thematic synthesis.

In step 8.1.1, one researcher read every selected study and extracted the data from each study according to the data model given in Figure 2. Accordingly, the data model structures the gathering and analysis of evidence regarding publications, the business service definitions studies propose, and the concerns adhered to by each definition (RQ-1).

Figure 2: Data Model for Data Extraction

The data model consists of three types of data entities: Publication, Business Service Definition, and Business Service Design Concern. The data scheme for each entity with the description of each attribute is given in Table 5. Accordingly, a publication proposes at least one business service definition and a definition

adheres to one or more business service design concerns. All the business service definitions we extracted with our data model are given in Appendix B - Table 14.

Table 5: The data scheme of the entities in the data model

Entity	Entity Description	Attribute	Attribute Description
Publication	A publication that includes a study proposing a business service definition	Authors (STRING)	List of the authors of the publication
		Title (STRING)	The title of the publication
		Publication Year (INT)	The year that the SIM was published
		Publication Type (STRING)	The type of publication (e.g., journal, conference proceeding, book chapter) that the SIM was published in
Business Service Definition	An instance of a business service definition proposed by the study	Definition Identifier (STRING)	The code given by the researchers to the business service definition
		Definition Type (STRING)	The type of the definition for business services (e.g., a textual definition, an ontology, or a model) proposed by the study.
		Definition Content (STRING)	The line, paragraph, chapter, model, ontology from the study that describes the technique used for identification.
Business Service Design Concern	An instance of a concern associated with the business service definition proposed in the study	Concern Identifier (STRING)	Code given by the researchers to the concern(s) that the business service definition adheres to in the form of concern keyword (e.g., "Customer-Orientation")
		Concern Description (STRING)	The description of the business service design concern

In Step 8.1.2, we coded each original definition (Table 14) to extract the business service design concerns following the guidelines given in Charmaz (2014). Accordingly, we created preliminary codes for the business service design concerns that each definition adheres to by using the tool Saturate (Sillito and De Alwis, 2009). The preliminary codes for the design concerns are provided in Appendix B - Table 15, and the traceability between business service definitions and preliminary codes is shown in Appendix B - Table 16.

In Step 8.1.3, we translated the preliminary codes (Table 15) into overarching themes by using *focused* or *axial coding* (Charmaz, 2014). In Step 8.1.4, we organized them into higher-order themes by identifying recurrent concepts and/or codes within them. The final set of business service design concerns is provided in Section 4.2.

Finally, in Step 8.1.5, we assessed the trustworthiness of our synthesis by mainly focusing on the bias concerning the extraction and coding of the results with discussions held between the authors of the paper. Furthermore, we performed an ex-ante, naturalistic evaluation via focus group to validate the completeness of the higher-order themes and the business service design concerns falling under them (Venable, Pries-Heje and Baskerville, 2016). In this evaluation, the first author discussed each higher-order theme and the underlying business service design concerns in a 90-minute-long meeting with four researchers who are experts in the fields of business architecture and business model design.

3.2.3 Steps of SLR-2

During our pilot searches, we observed that after retrieving studies on business services, locating the studies that propose SIMs with the keywords "identification" AND "method" is fairly straightforward as the studies demonstrate a consensus in referring to SIMs with these keywords. Therefore, we chose to use *database searches with a search string* as our strategy for locating relevant studies in SLR-2. The right side of Figure 1 shows the steps of the SLR procedure with the number of studies resulting from the execution of these steps.

To identify relevant studies, in Step 5.2, we first created inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 6) based on our research objective and RQ-2, RQ-3, and RQ-4. IC-1 relates to the study publication years and targets the early works on the business services and SIMs. Since the research objective of SLR-2 is to identify SIMs, we selected the studies that propose a unique SIM for the identification of business services (IC-2 and EC-4). Additionally, in our pilot searches, we observed that some SIMs focus on service discovery, which concerns discovering existing services rather than identifications (EC-3). Finally, we decided to exclude the studies that are not publicly available and not written in English (EC-1 and EC-2).

Table 6: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for SLR-2

Type of Criterion	ID	Description
Inclusion	IC-1	The study is published between 1-1-2000 and 1-6-2021.
Inclusion	IC-2	The study proposes a SIM for the identification of business services.
Exclusion	EC-1	The study is not publicly available in its complete form.
Exclusion	EC-2	The study is not written in English, which is the most common language in scientific publications.
Exclusion	EC-3	The study is on service discovery, which concerns discovering existing services.
Exclusion	EC-4	The study is referring to or applies a SIM originally published in previous study.

After creating the inclusion and exclusion criteria, we sorted the studies identified in Step 4 according to their relevance to our search string and applied the criteria IC- 1, EC-1, and 2 on the title, abstract, and keywords of the studies (Table 7). After this initial retrieval, we exported the resulting studies to spreadsheets, and we applied IC-2, EC-3, and EC-4, respectively, by targeting the title, abstract, and keyword of each study. Since the number of studies that returned from ScienceDirect and SpringerLink was too large (>1000), we used cut-off and threshold points before our relevancy scan. The number of studies that went through this procedure is shown in Table 7 under the “# Selected for Title, Abstract or Keywords” column.

Table 7: Number of Studies Initially Retrieved and Selected in Digital Libraries

Digital Library	# Initially Retrieved	# Selected for Title, Abstract, or Keywords	# Selected for Review
Ebsco	26	26	2
ScienceDirect	1134	1000	7
Scopus	614	614	51
SpringerLink	9605	1000	80
Web of Science	128	128	13
Wiley	224	224	1
Total	11731	2992	154

In Step 6.2, we removed duplicate studies before further reviewing the initial pool of studies (154 studies). This left us with 98 unique studies for the relevancy scan. In Step 7.2, we read the entire content of 98 studies and applied the IC-1, EC-3, and 4 again. This resulted in 38 studies being selected from the initial 98 studies. Then, we analysed the references of these 38 studies by applying a single iteration of backward and forward snowballing (Wohlin, 2014) and identified 9 additional studies that were not in the list of the initial search results. In the end, our selection resulted in a total of 47 studies as primary studies for data extraction and synthesis. The list of primary studies, hence SIMs, is given in Appendix B.

In Step 8.2, we created a data model (Figure 3) to structure the extraction and synthesis of data from the 47 primary studies (Cruzes and Dyba, 2011a) and thus to answer our research questions concerning the SIMs (RQ-2), the business service identification techniques that SIMs use (RQ-3), and the concerns adhered to by each technique and consequently by each SIM (RQ-4).

Figure 3: Data Model Used for Data Extraction

Our data model consists of three types of data entities: SIM (Method), Technique, and Business Service Design Concern. The data scheme introducing each entity, along with the descriptions of each attribute under that entity, is given in Table 8. Accordingly, a SIM uses at least one identification technique, whereas an identification technique adheres to zero, one, or more business service design concerns. The data regarding the SIM entity were directly extracted from the publications. To extract the data for the Technique entity, we conducted joint coding and analysis by following the constant comparative method (Glaser, 1965). In this regard, while extracting the techniques and coding them, we also compared each technique to the techniques coded by Hubbers et al. (Hubbers, Ligthart and Terlouw, 2007) and Gu & Lago (2010). This comparison resulted in splits and merges in certain categories of techniques. The resulting list of identified techniques is presented in Section 4.2.

Table 8: The Data Scheme of the Entities in the Data Model

Entity	Entity Description	Attribute	Attribute Description
SIM	The SIM proposed by a primary study	Publication Year (INT)	The year that the SIM was published
		Publication Type (STRING)	The type of publication (e.g., journal, conference proceeding, book chapter) that the SIM was published in
		Form of Evaluation (STRING)	The form of evaluation used to validate the identification technique (i.e., expert evaluation, case study, prototype) (Peffer <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Technique	An instance of a technique used by a specific SIM to identify business services	Technique Identifier (STRING)	The code given by the authors to the identification technique
		Technique Description (STRING)	The line, paragraph, or chapter from the study at the technique used for identification.
Business Service Design Concern	An instance of a concern that is adhered to by the specific technique used	Concern Identifier (STRING)	Code that is given to the concern(s) that the technique adheres to in the form of concern keyword (e.g., “Customer-Orientation”) as defined in the study classification scheme.
		Adherence Mechanism (STRING)	The key practice(s) a SIM follows to adhere to a specific concern (e.g., modelling the goal relationships between the service provider and service customer)

4 Findings

In this section, we present the findings of our SLRs in three parts: an overview of the selected studies for both SLRs (Section 4.1), design concerns associated with business services (Section 4.2), service identification techniques used by SIMs (Section 4.3), and the addressing of the business service design concerns by both service identification techniques and SIMs (Section 4.4).

4.1 An Overview of the Selected Studies

Overall, we identified 16 studies, each proposing a unique conceptualization of business services (Appendix A), and 47 studies, each introducing a unique SIM (Appendix C). The distribution of the selected studies according to the years in which they have been published and their types are given in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Distribution of the Selected Studies Per Year (left) and Per Type (right)

The distribution of the selected studies per year shows a wave of studies proposing business service conceptualizations and SIMs that start in 2004 and peak towards 2010. However, for SIMs, it should be noted that our selection of studies does not include publications that report on the application of a SIM that was reported in a previous publication. As for the type of publications, the majority (73%) of studies were published as conference proceedings, followed by journal articles (21%) and book chapters (6%).

4.2 Design Concerns Associated with Business Services – SLR-1

Our data extraction and synthesis for RQ-1 in the scope of SLR-1 resulted in the identification of 10 design concerns presented in Table 9. In the table, every row includes the number of the design concern, its code and short description, its full description, and a set of studies that propose the design concern.

Table 9: The Design Concerns Associated with Business Services

#	Bus. Service Design Concern	Description of the Concern	Sources
DC-1	Service Owner: A business service has a service owner	A business service is affiliated with a governing body that is responsible for the management (i.e., creation, maintenance, and delivery) of it. This governing body can be an enterprise, functional area, department, or organizational actor (Estrada <i>et al.</i> , 2013).	(Sanz and Becker, 2006; Estrada <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Hakanen and Jaakkola, 2012; Kwak and Kim, 2016).
DC-2	Goal-Oriented: A business service is connected to business goals and objectives of its service owner	A business service is designed to realize the strategic objectives of its service owner in creating competitive advantage by leveraging its unique set of capabilities and resources (Kwak and Kim, 2016).	(Flaxer and Nigam, 2004; Cherbakov <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sanz, Nayak and Becker, 2006; Ramel, Grandry and Dubois, 2009; Romero and Molina, 2009; Tohidi, 2011; Estrada <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Lusch and Nambisan, 2015; Lê <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Turetken <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
DC-3	Beneficiary-Oriented: A business service is beneficiary-facing (meaning that it aids beneficiaries in achieving their goals or to co-create value)	A business service enables its beneficiaries to accomplish their goals. In this sense, the service owner designs its business services according to the specific needs of a customer, customer segment, or market.	(Weigand <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Peña-Siles, del Mar González-Zamora and Machuca, 2012; Lê <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
DC-4	Value-Oriented: A business service is attuned to at least one value proposition	The ultimate purpose of every business service is to serve for the creation of value. Service providers have certain value propositions, which are invitations to engage in service for the co-creation of value (Patrício, Gustafsson and Fisk, 2018; Gilsing <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Jungerius <i>et al.</i> , 2022). Business services are explicitly linked to these value propositions and implicitly to value co-creation.	(Flaxer and Nigam, 2004; Sanz and Becker, 2006; Papazoglou, 2007; Weigand <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Adam, Naab and Trapp, 2010)

#	Bus. Service Design Concern	Description of the Concern	Sources
DC-5	<i>Capability-Encapsulation:</i> A business service offers a self-contained business capability or a set of related business capabilities	A business service is composed of a set of business capabilities that the service owner offers to its network for value creation. In defining the notion of capability in this design concern, we adopted the capability definition by Loucopoulos et al. (2016) which constituted by the lines “A particular ability or capacity that a business may possess or exchange to achieve a specific purpose or outcome. A capability describes what the business does (outcomes and service levels) that creates value for customers; for example, pay employee or ship product.”	(Karakostas, Zorgios and Alevizos, 2006; Sanz and Becker, 2006; Tians <i>et al.</i> , 2006; Papazoglou, 2007; Kohlborn <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Ramel, Grandry and Dubois, 2009; Barroero, Motta and Pignatelli, 2010; Estrada <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Peña-Siles, del Mar González-Zamora and Machuca, 2012; Loucopoulos <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Lê <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
DC-6	<i>Resource-Encapsulation:</i> A business service encapsulates a re-configuration of basic intangible and tangible resources	A business service is further composed of a combination of basic tangible and intangible resources required to offer the set of business capabilities that the business service is composed of. These resources can be consumed or used by the business service (McCarthy, 1982a).	(Karakostas, Zorgios and Alevizos, 2006; Weigand <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Zdravkovic and Ilayeruma, 2010; Peña-Siles, del Mar González-Zamora and Machuca, 2012; Lê <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
DC-7	<i>Formalization:</i> A business service has a formal description that explicitly lists all the characteristics of that business service to be kept in a service portfolio	Each business service is documented according to a formal description that is designed to ensure an understanding of business services amongst and between internal and external stakeholders.	(Peña-Siles, del Mar González-Zamora and Machuca, 2012; Lê <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
DC-8	<i>Delivery Mechanism:</i> A business service has mechanisms (i.e., business processes) that realize its delivery	A business service is delivered or made available to beneficiaries through business processes designed for service delivery (Karakostas, Zorgios and Alevizos, 2006). These business processes act as touchpoints where service interactions take place (Lê <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Suratno <i>et al.</i> , 2018).	(Karakostas, Zorgios and Alevizos, 2006; Lê <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
DC-9	<i>Uniqueness:</i> A business service is unique, meaning that there is no other business service offering the same business capabilities	A business service is composed of unique capabilities and resources. Accordingly, this design concern suggests service owners give precedence to re-configuration of their unique capabilities and resources into business services and outsource their not-so-unique business services.	(Sanz and Becker, 2006; Papazoglou, 2007; Weigand <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
DC-10	<i>Replicability:</i> A business service is replicable across value propositions	A business service is replicated among different value propositions that a service owner is involved in. Since unique business services are the source of competitive advantage, replicability focuses on the replicability of <i>unique</i> business services.	(Weigand <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Barroero, Motta and Pignatelli, 2010; Estrada <i>et al.</i> , 2010)

4.3 The SIMs and Techniques Used by SIMs to Identify Business Services – SLR-2

Our data extraction and synthesis for RQ-2 in the scope of SLR-2 resulted in the identification of 47 SIMs (Appendix C). To provide an understanding of the extent to which the proposed SIMs have been evaluated (for their validity, utility, efficacy, etc.), we investigated the forms of evaluation that are used in the primary studies to evaluate the proposed SIMs. Peffers et al. (2012) reports eight forms of evaluation techniques that can be used for evaluating a design artifact (e.g., a SIM): logical argumentation, expert evaluation, technical experiment, subject-based experiment, action research, prototype, case study, and illustrative scenario. However, we only observed the use of two of these evaluation techniques in primary studies. These are case studies and illustrative scenarios. Furthermore, several studies do not report on any form of

evaluation applied for the SIMs they propose. The details of the evaluation technique types are presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Forms of Evaluation Used for SIMs

Form of Evaluation*	Description	Frequency	SIMs
Case Study	Application of an artifact to a real-world situation and evaluating its effect on that specific business setting.	14	SIM-9, SIM-10, SIM-11, SIM-13, SIM-14, SIM-15, SIM-17, SIM-22, SIM-27, SIM-28, SIM-30, SIM-34, SIM-45, SIM-46
Illustrative Scenario	Application of an artifact to a synthetic or real-world situation aimed at illustrating the suitability or utility of the artifact.	25	SIM-1, SIM-7, SIM-8, SIM-12, SIM-16, SIM-18, SIM-19, SIM-20, SIM-21, SIM-23, SIM-24, SIM-25, SIM-26, SIM-31, SIM-32, SIM-33, SIM-36, SIM-37, SIM-38, SIM-40, SIM-41, SIM-42, SIM-43, SIM-44, SIM-47
NA	The information on evaluation is not present.	8	SIM-2, SIM-3, SIM-4, SIM-5, SIM-6, SIM-29, SIM-35, SIM-39

*Taken from (Peffer et al., 2012)

Apart from the SIMs, per RQ-3, we also synthesized the techniques employed in the SIMs into 13 distinct techniques. Each technique is a procedure specifically designed to identify business services. A procedure focuses on a key business artifact (e.g., business processes, goals, business functions, features) and includes a set of activities that employ this artifact in identifying business services. Each row of Table 11 refers to one of these techniques and provides a brief description of the technique, the frequency of the technique, and the SIMs that use the technique.

Table 11: Business Service Identification Techniques

#	Technique	Description	Frequency	SIMs
T-1	Business Process Decomposition	Business process models are decomposed into cohesive activity clusters which represent candidate business services	21	SIM-2, SIM-3, SIM-4, SIM-6, SIM-8, SIM-9, SIM-11, SIM-13, SIM-16, SIM-17, SIM-22, SIM-23, SIM-27, SIM-28, SIM-29, SIM-30, SIM-33, SIM-34, SIM-42, SIM-45, SIM-46
T-2	Goal Decomposition	The goal relationships between the service provider and service receivers are determined and translated into business services.	12	SIM-1, SIM-10, SIM-15, SIM-18, SIM-21, SIM-24, SIM-29, SIM-31, SIM-37, SIM-40, SIM-41
T-3	Business Functions Analysis	The core business of the service provider (i.e., what a service provider does) is analyzed and decomposed into business services.	9	SIM-7, SIM-12, SIM-17, SIM-18, SIM-21, SIM-24, SIM-31, SIM-32, SIM-47
T-4	Ownership & Responsibility Determination	Ownership & responsibility regarding processes, functions, or goals are taken into consideration during business service identification. This technique is always used with other techniques such as process decomposition (SIM-11 and SIM-34), business functions analysis (SIM-7, SIM-18, SIM-24, SIM-31, and SIM-32), goal-driven (SIM-1, SIM-10, SIM-18, SIM-24, and SIM-31), and customer-driven (SIM-44).	10	SIM-1, SIM-7, SIM-10, SIM-11, SIM-18, SIM-24, SIM-31, SIM-32, SIM-34, SIM-44
T-5	Value Modelling	Value creating activities or resources of the business are analyzed and clustered into business services	4	SIM-25, SIM-38, SIM-41, SIM-45
T-6	Feature Modelling	A set of common or shared features of a software product family is converted into business services	3	SIM-14, SIM-19, SIM-46
T-7	Business Entity Analysis	Operations done on information entities by software are used to determine business services	2	SIM-20, SIM-26

#	Technique	Description	Frequency	SIMs
T-8	Business Component Decomposition	Service Provider's organizational structure is divided into high-level autonomous components and interactions between these components and service receivers are modelled as business services	1	SIM-5
T-9	Legacy Asset Analysis	The existing information system of the Service Provider is analyzed, and its functions are exposed as business services	1	SIM-35
T-10	Business Use Case Analysis	Interactions between customers and service providers are converted into business services	3	SIM-13, SIM-32, SIM-36
T-11	Enterprise Ontology Based	Business services are derived from enterprise ontology	1	SIM-39
T-12	Agent-oriented	Service providers and service customers are modelled as agents and their (agent) goals are analyzed and translated into business services	1	SIM-43
T-13	Customer-driven	Customers' interaction with the service provider is analyzed, modelled, and translated into business services	2	SIM-44, SIM-47

4.4 The extent to which the Business Service Design concerns are addressed by Techniques and SIMs – SLR-2

To determine the extent to which each business service design concern is addressed by a specific technique (RQ-4), we checked whether a specific technique fully or partially fulfills the conditions given in the definition of each concern (Table 9). As an example, the full coverage of DC-1: *Goal-Orientation* requires a technique to explicitly connect each identified business service to one or more business goals. Thus, the techniques that explicitly link business goals to business services are classified as "Fully Addressed" concerning DC-1: *Goal Orientation*.

In Table 12, we present a mapping between the techniques and the business service design concerns and indicate the degree to which a certain technique addresses a business service design concern. In this regard, the more the number of the fully addressed ('✓') and partially addressed ('O') appear in a technique row, the more successful the technique is at addressing business service design concerns. Similarly, the more the number of the '✓'s and 'O's in a business service design concern column, the more effective the techniques are at addressing this concern. In the paragraphs below, we provide our findings for each business service design concern in detail.

4.4.1 DC-1: Service Owner

The techniques T-4: *Ownership and Responsibility*, T-7: *Business Entity Analysis*, T-8: *Business Component Decomposition*, and T-12: *Agent-oriented* fully address this concern by drawing a line between governing bodies and clearly defining who owns which business service and which business service is under whose responsibility. The techniques T-2: *Goal Decomposition*, T-3: *Business Function Analysis*, and T-11: *Enterprise Ontology Based* partially address this concern as they focus on one organizational entity rather than collaborating entities.

4.4.2 DC-2: Goal-Orientation

Overall, 8 techniques consider the link between business services and business goals. Out of these, T-2: *Goal Decomposition*, T-8: *Business Component Decomposition*, and T-12: *Agent-oriented* explicitly determine the business goals of the service provider and cluster the identified business services underneath the business goals they serve. The remaining 5 of the original 8 fail to fully address the concern as they are implicit in terms of the link between a specific business service and a specific business goal.

4.4.3 DC-3: Beneficiary-Orientation

Overall, 6 techniques consider beneficiary goals in identifying business services. These techniques are T-1: *Business Process Decomposition*, T-2: *Goal Decomposition*, T-3: *Business Function Analysis*, T-4: *Ownership*

& Responsibility, T-12: Agent-oriented, and T-13: Customer-driven. However, only T-12: Agent-oriented, and T-13: Customer-driven, fully address this concern, as they model the goal relationships between the service owner and beneficiaries and identify a business service for each goal relationship. Others fail to capture the goal relationships as they focus on the service owner's business goals.

Table 12: A Mapping of Business Service Design Concerns and Identification Techniques

#	Business Service Identification Techniques	Business Service Design Concerns									
		DC-1: Service Owner	DC-2: Goal-Oriented	DC-3: Beneficiary-Oriented	DC-4: Value Orientation	DC-5: Capability-Encapsulation	DC-6: Resource-Encapsulation	DC-7: Formalization	DC-8: Delivery Mechanism	DC-9: Uniqueness	DC-10: Replicability
T-1	Business Process Decomposition	-	O	O	O	O	O	✓	✓	O	O
T-2	Goal Decomposition	O	✓	O	O	O	✓	O	-	-	-
T-3	Business Functions Analysis	O	O	O	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
T-4	Ownership & Resp. Determination	✓	-	O	-	O	-	✓	-	-	-
T-5	Value Modelling	-	O	-	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-
T-6	Feature Modelling	-	-	-	-	O	-	✓	-	✓	✓
T-7	Business Entity Analysis	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-
T-8	Business Component Decomposition	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
T-9	Legacy Asset Analysis	-	-	-	-	O	-	✓	-	-	-
T-10	Business Use Case Analysis	-	O	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
T-11	Enterprise Ontology-Based	O	-	-	-	-	-	O	-	-	-
T-12	Agent-oriented	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-
T-13	Customer-driven	-	O	✓	-	O	-	✓	-	-	-

Legend: ✓ = Fully Addressed, O = Partially Addressed, - = Not Addressed

4.4.4 DC-4: Value Orientation

Only T-5: *Value Modelling* ensures that identified business services are linked to the value propositions of their service owner. This technique starts identifying business services by modeling the value propositions of the service owner. Next, it identifies the business functionalities aimed at creating the values as defined by value propositions, thereby linking business services to value propositions. Apart from T-5: *Value Modelling*, T-1: *Business Process Decomposition*, and T-2: *Goal Decomposition* techniques can relate value propositions to business services when there is an existing link between business processes and goals, and value propositions. However, this requires an existing model of value propositions and matching between value propositions and processes and goals. Therefore, they partially address this concern.

4.4.5 DC-5: Capability-Encapsulation

In total, 9 techniques determine the business capabilities that the business services they identify capture. Three out of these 9 (T-3: *Business Functions Analysis*, T-8: *Business Component Decomposition*, and T-10: *Business Use Case Analysis*) analyze the core business of the service owner and identify business functions that the service provider uses to interact with service receivers. The remaining 6 fail to fully address the concern as they implicitly relate business services to business functionality, but do not specify the business functionalities per business service.

4.4.6 DC-6: Resource-Encapsulation

Only 2 techniques explicitly consider the resources affiliated with business services. These techniques are T-2: *Goal Decomposition* and T-5: *Value Modelling*. Both techniques model the interactions between the service provider and service receivers in terms of exchanged resources and cluster them into resource combinations according to the business goals and/or value propositions. T-1: *Business Process*

Decomposition partially addresses this concern, as it models the resources business processes use, but not necessarily the resources that each business service uses.

4.4.7 DC-7: Formalization

All techniques create business service descriptions documenting the properties of the business services they identify. Furthermore, all techniques create service hierarchies, or communication and/or interaction models between business services that detail the connections between business services and other business artifacts (the type of the business artifact usually depends on the technique). Unlike the others, the techniques *T-2: Goal Decomposition* and *T-11: Enterprise Ontology Based* do not include different perspectives providing relevant information for various stakeholders. Therefore, they only partially address this concern.

4.4.8 DC-8: Delivery Mechanism

Out of 13 techniques, we identified only 2 techniques that specify the delivery mechanism of the business services it identifies. The first technique, *T-1: Business Process Decomposition*, explicitly focuses on business processes and clusters them under business services. Thus, it automatically specifies and bundles the business processes that are required for the delivery of the business services it identifies. The second technique, *T-5: Value Modelling*, determines the delivery mechanisms of business services by explicitly defining the business processes that realize service delivery alongside the policy that governs these processes.

4.4.9 DC-9: Uniqueness

We identified only one technique that takes the uniqueness of the business services that it identifies into consideration, and that technique is *T-6: Feature Modelling*. It involves the means (e.g., variation modeling) and accompanying measures (e.g., variability points) to ensure and later assess the uniqueness of the identified set of business services based on software product families. Apart from *T-6: Feature Modelling*, *T-1: Business Process Decomposition* partially addresses this intention. *Business Process Decomposition* involves the means (e.g., label matching on business processes) and accompanying measures (e.g., functional overlaps in business processes) to ensure the uniqueness of the business service it identifies. However, it does not involve any means to measure or check the uniqueness of the resulting set of business services.

4.4.10 DC-10: Replicability

Matching the findings for DC-9: Uniqueness, we identified only a single technique that takes the replicability of business services that it identifies into consideration, and that technique is *T-6: Feature Modelling*. By incorporating concepts such as feature binding units and feature binding times, this technique aims to ensure the replicability of the business services it identifies by incorporating service-oriented architecture measures of low coupling and cohesion. Similarly, *T-1: Business Process Decomposition* clusters business processes that are related to a business service (e.g., cohesion). However, it does not explicitly address other concerns that relate to replicability, such as the coupling between business services in terms of the information entities passed between business services. Therefore, *T-1: Business Process Decomposition* only partially addresses this concern.

The business service identification technique vs. design concern mapping explicates the extent of coverage of each concern on the technique level. However, it does not show the extent of coverage of the concerns on the SIM level, as some SIMs combine multiple techniques (e.g., SIM-1, SIM-18, or SIM-24). To address this issue, we extended our mapping to the level of SIMs by building upon the technique-business service design concern mapping. This mapping between SIMs and the business service design concerns that they adhere to is presented in Appendix C. Notably, *SIM-18*, *SIM-24*, and *SIM-41* fully address the highest number of concerns (5 out of 10, in this case). However, while *SIM-18* and *SIM-24* partially address only 2 concerns next to the concerns they fully address, *SIM-41* partially addresses 3. Therefore, *SIM-41*, proposed by Lee, Sugumaran, Park, and Sansi (2011), stands out as the best SIM in terms of the extent of coverage of the business service design concerns. It incorporates two different techniques: *T-2: Goal Decomposition* and *T-5: Value Modelling*.

5 Discussion

Looking at the overview of the selected studies (Figure 4), the distribution of the studies proposing conceptualizations of business services and SIMs over the years shows that the research concerning business service identification has reached a saturation point and is currently at stagnation. This can lead to the assumption that the business services as an architectural construct and SIMs as operational procedures using this construct together provide sufficient support to organizations in the identification of business services, and therefore, they have achieved widespread acceptance in practice.

However, our findings with respect to the forms of evaluations used for SIMs (Table 10) lead to the observation that only a handful of studies in the current literature feature an application and comprehensive evaluation of the proposed SIMs in real-world settings. A significant majority of the proposed SIMs have been evaluated only through illustrative scenarios. Furthermore, an important number of SIMs have not been subjected to any form of evaluation. Therefore, it can be argued that the effectiveness of the existing SIMs in the identification of business services is still open to discussions and contributions.

Similarly, our findings with respect to the extent to which the business service design concerns are addressed by the techniques and SIMs also raise questions about the effectiveness of the SIMs. As such, our findings show that the SIMs and the techniques they employ are lacking in terms of providing sufficient guidance to organizations in addressing all the design concerns associated with business services (see Table 12 and Table 17). This issue has been highlighted by Bani-Ismael & Baghdadi (Bani-Ismael and Baghdadi, 2018), where a lack of a comprehensive SIM for the identification of service elements has been found to be a major challenge.

Our findings also show that each concern defined by the literature is addressed by at least one technique. This implies that combining the key practices of techniques into the form of a comprehensive SIM can be practical, as the application of such a SIM can potentially yield business services that are fully aligned with all concerns. Recognizing this, we have grouped SIMs by the concerns they address and analyzed the key practices they follow to adhere to a specific concern. We summarize a set of high-level practices -which we refer to as *key practices*- as presented in Table 13.

Table 13: Key Practices synthesized by grouping SIMs according to the design concerns they address

#	Design Concern	Key Practices
DC-1	Service Owner	Determine the governing body of the business service according to the business functionality and/or resources encapsulated in the business service. The governing body which owns the business functionality and/or resources is the owner of the business service.
DC-2	Goal-Orientation	Determine the business goals of the service owner and cluster the identified business services underneath the business goals they help to realize
DC-3	Beneficiary-Orientation	Model the goal relationships between the service owner and beneficiaries, then identify a business service for each goal relationship.
DC-4	Value Orientation	Model the value propositions of the service owner and identify the business capabilities aimed to create each value.
DC-5	Capability-Encapsulation	Analyze the core business of the service owner and identify business capabilities that the service owner uses to interact with the beneficiaries.
DC-6	Resource-Encapsulation	Model the interactions between the service provider and service customers in terms of exchanged resources and cluster them into resource combinations according to the business processes, value propositions, and/or business goals.
DC-7	Formalization	Specify the properties of each business service by using a template that is catered to document all the business artifacts associated with business services
DC-8	Delivery Mechanism	Specify the business process that realizes service delivery alongside the policy that governs this process.
DC-9	Uniqueness	During the identification of the business services, ensure that each business service is representative of a domain-specific service. For that check for the commonalities (e.g., facilitation of same service operations) and differences (e.g., creation of value for a new customer segment) between business services. Cluster the commonalities into cohesive business services and isolate the differences into novel business services.
DC-10	Replicability	Ensure that the business services identified are self-contained (i.e., consist of cohesive service operations) and stateless (i.e., does not rely upon other business services in terms of contextual information).

Overall, the findings of our study show that the business service concept provides the necessary guidelines to model the functional elements of a service architecture, and SIMs provide guidance to use the business service concept for that purpose. Specifically, we observed an alignment between the design concerns incorporated in the business service concept and service management challenges reported in the literature, such as achieving customization and standardization in service offerings (Böttcher and Klingner, 2011), efficiency in service operations (Estrada *et al.*, 2013), or openness in service provision (Sanz and Becker, 2006). This provides further evidence in support of the potential utility of the approach in the context of service architecture. However, the limitations concerning the effectiveness of the approach seem to impede its utility and widespread adoption in practice. Research should address the gaps regarding the lack of a comprehensive SIM and comprehensive evaluations of the effectiveness of such a SIM in real-world settings.

6 Conclusion

In this study, we report on a structured review of the literature on business service design concerns, the SIMs, and the techniques proposed for the identification of business services. More specifically, in our review, we investigated the extent to which the proposed SIMs and techniques address the concerns intrinsic to the concept of business service. In conducting the review, we performed a search on 6 well-established digital libraries to find relevant studies published in the years between 2000 and 2021 (June).

In response to our research questions, we identified 10 business service design concerns (Table 9) through coding and thematic analysis of business service conceptualizations in the literature (RQ-1). We identified 47 unique SIMs that guide the identification of business services (RQ-2). Our exploration of the techniques that SIMs follow to identify business services (RQ-3) resulted in a set of 13 distinct techniques (Table 11). Finally, to clarify the extent to which the business service design concerns are addressed by the service identification techniques and by SIMs (RQ-4), we mapped the 10 business service design concerns onto 13 techniques (Table 12) and consequently onto 47 SIMs (Table 17). In the mappings, we indicated the degree to which a certain technique and a SIM address a business service design concern.

Our study provides an overview of the state-of-the-art research on business service identification, including the research gaps and improvement points that should be addressed in future research. Researchers and practitioners can consider our review as a comprehensive source to understand the current SIMs and techniques they use to identify business services, including the gaps and improvement points for more comprehensive business service identification. A major gap we identified is that none of the existing techniques and SIMs address the entire set of design concerns reported in the literature regarding the identification of business services. However, the key practices we identified can be a starting point for the design of a comprehensive SIM that can accomplish the task. In this regard, researchers can use our findings as a guide in the design of new SIMs or the improvement of existing ones. The practitioners seeking ways to design a service architecture for their organizations, our findings can provide guidance in selecting the most suitable techniques and SIMs to address their needs.

This study has various limitations regarding the searches employed and the study analysis scheme used. In terms of the searches, our initial search excluded the work in the grey literature, which includes work-in-progress studies, publications without bibliographic information, unpublished works, technical reports, and white papers. Future work might focus on conducting reviews in these non-academic contexts to unfold business service conceptualizations and SIMs not covered by our study. Other limitations concerning the searches are the search string used to survey digital libraries and the inclusion and exclusion criteria used in selecting the studies. For instance, using a non-restrictive search string resulted in a large set of initially retrieved studies, and as a result, we employed a comprehensive filtering process to identify the relevant studies. While we ensured the rigor of the filtering process by following established protocols, some relevant studies not being included in our final selection still poses a risk. Similarly, the final set of studies can be missing relevant studies due to inclusion and exclusion criteria, even though we used backward and forward snowballing techniques in both SLRs to mitigate the risk of missing relevant works. Although these are in line with our research objectives, they pose risks for the completeness and validity of the findings. Concerning SLR-1, although, we aimed to create a comprehensive list of concerns, both the approach to

create this list and the resulting list of concerns remain to be non-exhaustive. As such, there can be some design concerns that are not covered, or that should not be in the final list of concerns. This poses additional risks for the findings of SLR-2 as the study analysis scheme used for analyzing SIMs and techniques is built upon the list of design concerns that we synthesized. Future work should focus on validating or modifying our list of design concerns.

As an additional threat to the validity of our conclusions, we acknowledge that this research provides a limited understanding of the use of the business service concept and SIMs in practical settings. Hence, future work can be directed towards comparative application studies in real-life business settings involving quantitative/empirical studies – also in the form of longitudinal case studies - to better demonstrate the validity and effectiveness of the business service concept and SIMs.

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Appendix A The Selected Studies for Business Service Design Concerns

Studies marked with a '' indicate those in the starting set.

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- [BSD-5.] *Estrada, H., Martínez, A., Pastor, O., Mylopoulos, J., & Giorgini, P. (2010). Extending Organizational Modeling with Business Services Concepts: An Overview of the Proposed Architecture (pp. 483–488). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16373-9_39
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- [BSD-7.] *Karakostas, B., Zorgios, Y., & Alevizos, C. C. (2006). The Semantics of Business Service Orchestration (pp. 435–446). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/11837862_41
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- [BSD-10.] *Papazoglou, M. P. (2007). What's in a Service? In Software Architecture (pp. 11–28). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-75132-8_3
- [BSD-11.] Peña-Siles, J., del Mar González-Zamora, M., & Machuca, J. A. D. (2012). Specifying business services: learning from software engineering. Journal of Service Management, 23(1), 97–119. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09564231211208998>
- [BSD-12.] Ramel, S., Grandry, E., & Dubois, E. (2009). Towards a Design Method Supporting the Alignment between Business and Services Software. In Proceedings - International Computer Software and Applications Conference (Vol. 1, pp. 349–354). Seattle, WA. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMPSAC.2009.53>
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Appendix B By Products of Thematic Synthesis

Table 14: Business Service Definitions Extracted from each Selected Paper

BSD #	Business Service Definition	Source
BSD-01	<p>“Business services are deliveries of capabilities to consumers.”</p> <p>“A business service is modelled as consisting of a number of inputs, outputs, controls and mechanisms:</p> <p>Inputs denote the capabilities that are required for the provision of the service.</p> <p>Outputs are the capabilities offered by the service to its consumers.</p> <p>Controls are the methods, procedures, standards etc. controlling the provision of the service.</p> <p>Finally, mechanisms are the processes and resources used in the provision of the service.”</p>	(Karakostas, Zorgios and Alevizos, 2006)
BSD-02	<p>“A business service is usually based on grouping of business functionalities. The grouping may be based on workflow, tasks, activities, and often include implicit or explicit rules.”</p>	(Tians <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
BSD-03	<p>“A business service is an interface through which other components requires or provides a capability. It is standardized and hides its implementation from other components.”</p>	(Barroero, Motta and Pignatelli, 2010)
BSD-04	<p>“A business service automates a generic business task with significance to the business, e.g., creating a customer record, creating an invoice or closing an open customer service ticket. It provides value to an enterprise and is part of standard business process.”</p>	(Papazoglou, 2007)
BSD-05	<p>“We have defined a business service as a functionality that an organizational entity (an enterprise, functional area, department, or organizational actor) offers to other entities in order to fulfill its goals.”</p>	(Estrada <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
BSD-06	<p>“A business service is a service provided by a business unit that is of immaterial value for at least one other business unit.”</p>	(Adam, Naab and Trapp, 2010)
BSD-07	<p>“...a Business Service is the business architecture entity that represents the outcome of a significantly large “chunk of operation” in a company.”</p>	(Sanz and Becker, 2006)
BSD-08	<p>“A business service is some welldefined value that a business component offers to other business components and/or to external parties.”</p>	(Flaxer and Nigam, 2004)
BSD-09	<p>Proposes a 3x3x3 Grid that proposes three dimensions that represent business services: service consumers, service provider, and service context.</p> <p>“The dimension of the service consumers has three concepts: received value, service input/output and service bundling/unbundling (combining or removing various business services according to customer needs).”</p> <p>“In the dimension of the service providers, the concepts that matter are the returned/co-created value, the service capability and service composition/decomposition.”</p> <p>“The dimension of service context features objective (business objectives), norm (Obligations, prohibitions and permissions that govern interaction between actors involved in value co-creation) and touchpoint (where service interactions happen).”</p>	(Lê <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
BSD-10	<p>“A business service is an economic service provided by an economic actor to fulfil a customer need. A (business) service is a resource as it is viewed as valuable by some agent and can be exchanged between agents. A distinctive feature of a (business) service is that it has a goal to modify (and hence add value to) other resources. For example, the goal of the hairdressing service is to convert the customer’s hair. A (business) service does not specify how it is to be realized, i.e. how its goals are to be achieved. Instead, a service can be realized in many different ways.”</p>	(Weigand <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
BSD-11	<p>“Presenting business logic of a transaction or a business entity. The purpose of the service ... as business logic, or as specific domain functions (e.g. a service for customer credit check).”</p>	(Alahmari, De Roure and Zaluska, 2010)
BSD-12	<p>“...the functional business part of these (business) services directly contributes to the creation of value in a networked value constellation according to the strategy defined by an organization.”</p>	(Ramel, Grandry and Dubois, 2009)
BSD-13	<p>“business services... created to realize and/or support the delivery of economic resources.”</p>	(Zdravkovic and Ilayperuma, 2010)

BSD #	Business Service Definition	Source
BSD-14	“Business services are created to support the exchange of business values across a network of enterprises.”	(Cherbakov <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
BSD-15	“In this paper, we use the term business service to refer to an autonomous transformational capability that is offered to and consumed by external or internal customers for their benefit.”	(Kohlborn <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
BSD-16	“(1) Resource model (structure dimension): the resources required for the service to be provided correctly, comprising human resource capabilities, such as the definition of the skills required by the staff involved, information systems required, etc. (2) Process model (process dimension): describes how the outcomes of the service are achieved. (3) Product model (outcome dimension): describes what a service does and its outcomes (tangible and intangible).”	(Peña-Siles, del Mar González-Zamora and Machuca, 2012)

Table 15: Preliminary Business Service Design Concern Codes

#	Preliminary Business Service Design Concern Code	Preliminary Business Service Design Concern	Description of the Concern (As summarized from the papers)
PDC-01	<i>Goal-Orientation</i>	A business service shall be connected to business goals and objectives	Business services collectively support the achievement of business goals of the service provider. Therefore, each business service serves for the achievement of one or more business goals.
PDC-02	<i>Functionality/Capability -Orientation</i>	A business service shall encapsulate a business functionality/capability	A business service encapsulates a specific functionality/capability which service provider offers to its network for value creation. This functionality is obtained by service beneficiaries and used in their own context within their own activities.
PDC-03	<i>Resource-Based</i>	A business service shall encapsulate combinations of basic intangible and tangible resources	A business service encapsulates a combination of basic tangible and intangible resources required to offer the specific functionality. These resources can be consumed or used by the business service (McCarthy, 1982a).
PDC-04	<i>Customer-Orientation</i>	A business service shall be customer-facing - external	A business service enables its service beneficiaries to accomplish their goals. In this sense, service provider designs its business services according to the specific needs of a customer, customer segment or market.
PDC-05	<i>Value-Orientation</i>	A business service shall be connected to one or more value propositions	The ultimate purpose of every business service is to serve for creation of value. Service providers have certain value propositions which are invitations for engaging in service for the co-creation of value (Patrício, Gustafsson and Fisk, 2018). Business services are explicitly linked to these value propositions and implicitly to value co-creation.
PDC-06	<i>Service Owner</i>	A business service shall have a service owner	A business service is affiliated to a governing body that is responsible for the management (i.e., creation, maintenance, and delivery) of it. This governing body can be an enterprise, functional area, department, or organizational actor (Estrada <i>et al.</i> , 2013).

#	Preliminary Business Service Design Concern Code	Preliminary Business Service Design Concern	Description of the Concern (As summarized from the papers)
PDC-07	<i>Communication Interface</i>	A business service shall have a well-defined interface that explicates to the service customer how to interact with the business service	A business service has a communication interface. This interface sets the rules of communication with the business service and governs the business service's behavior according to the parameters used during communication.
PDC-08	<i>Delivery Mechanism</i>	A business service shall have mechanisms that realize its delivery	A business service is delivered to service customers via a specific delivery mechanism that outlines how service customer experiences the business service (e.g., interactive service processes).
PDC-09	<i>Composability</i>	A business service shall be composed into value proposition	A value proposition is a composition or aggregation of business services (e.g., services for the internal use of the service provider) that collectively enable the co-creation of value in a specific context.
PDC-10	<i>Standardization</i>	A business service shall follow a formal description that explicitly lists all the characteristics of that business service	Each business service is documented according to a formal description that is designed to ensure an understanding of business services amongst and between internal and external stakeholders.
PDC-11	<i>Loose Coupling</i>	A business service's dependencies to other business services shall be explicitly defined and minimized.	A value proposition may consist of multiple business services. The dependencies between these services must be limited to a number set by the service owner or value co-creation network actors.
PDC-12	<i>Reuse</i>	A business service shall be used in making multiple value propositions	Regardless of whether immediate reuse opportunities exist, business services are designed to support potential reuse (Estrada <i>et al.</i> , 2013).
PDC-13	<i>Encapsulation</i>	A business service shall encapsulate a business functionality/capability and a combination of basic tangible and intangible resources required to offer the specific functionality/capability.	The capabilities and resources beyond a business service are invisible to service beneficiaries.
PDC-14	<i>Service Portfolio</i>	All the information regarding a business service is stored in a service portfolio	One common way to manage multiple business services and communicate information regarding the business services is to store (Arsanjani <i>et al.</i> , 2008; Kohlborn <i>et al.</i> , 2009). These artifacts provide different perspectives to the business services and these perspectives include varying types of information with respect to different needs of different stakeholders (Harkonen, Tolonen and Haapasalo, 2017).

Table 16: A Mapping between Business Service Definitions and Business Service Design Concerns

BSD #	Business Service Definition	Business Service Design Concern Code
BSD-01	<p>“Business services are deliveries of capabilities to consumers.”</p> <p>“A business service is modelled as consisting of a number of inputs, outputs, controls and mechanisms: Inputs denote the capabilities that are required for the provision of the service. Outputs are the capabilities offered by the service to its consumers. Controls are the methods, procedures, standards etc. controlling the provision of the service. Finally, mechanisms are the processes and resources used in the provision of the service.”</p>	<p>Functionality-/Capability-Orientation</p> <p>Delivery Mechanism</p> <p>Resource-Based</p> <p>Customer-Orientation</p> <p>Communication Interface</p>
BSD-02	<p>“A business service is usually based on grouping of business functionalities. The grouping may be based on workflow, tasks, activities, and often include implicit or explicit rules.”</p>	<p>Functionality-/Capability-Orientation</p>
BSD-03	<p>“A business service is an interface through which other components requires or provides a capability. It is standardized and hides its implementation from other components.”</p>	<p>Functionality-/Capability-Orientation</p> <p>Standardization</p> <p>Encapsulation</p>
BSD-04	<p>“A business service automates a generic business task with significance to the business, e.g., creating a customer record, creating an invoice or closing an open customer service ticket. It provides value to an enterprise and is part of standard business process.”</p>	<p>Goal-Orientation</p> <p>Value-Orientation</p> <p>Customer-Orientation</p>
BSD-05	<p>“We have defined a business service as a functionality that an organizational entity (an enterprise, functional area, department, or organizational actor) offers to other entities in order to fulfill its goals.”</p>	<p>Functionality-/Capability-Orientation</p> <p>Service Owner</p> <p>Goal-Orientation</p> <p>Encapsulation</p> <p>Loose Coupling</p> <p>Composability</p> <p>Reusability</p> <p>Catalogue</p>
BSD-06	<p>“A business service is a service provided by a business unit that is of immaterial value for at least one other business unit.</p>	<p>Service Owner</p> <p>Value-Orientation</p>
BSD-07	<p>“...a Business Service is the business architecture entity that represents the outcome of a significantly large “chunk of operation” in a company.”</p>	<p>Goal-Orientation</p> <p>Customer-Orientation</p>
BSD-08	<p>“A business service is some well-defined value that a business component offers to other business components and/or to external parties.”</p>	<p>Standardization</p> <p>Service Owner</p> <p>Customer-Orientation</p>
BSD-09	<p>Proposes a 3x3x3 Grid that proposes three dimensions that represent business services: service consumers, service provider, and service context.</p> <p>“The dimension of the service consumers has three concepts: received value, service input/output and service bundling/unbundling (combining or removing various business services according to customer needs).”</p> <p>“In the dimension of the service providers, the concepts that matter are the returned/co-created value, the service capability and service composition/decomposition.”</p> <p>“The dimension of service context features objective (business objectives), norm (Obligations, prohibitions and permissions that govern interaction between actors involved in value co-creation) and touchpoint (where service interactions happen).”</p>	<p>Functionality-/Capability-Orientation</p> <p>Goal-Orientation</p> <p>Customer-Orientation</p> <p>Composability</p>

BSD #	Business Service Definition	Business Service Design Concern Code
BSD-10	<p>“A business service is an economic service provided by an economic actor to fulfill a customer need. A (business) service is a resource as it is viewed as valuable by some agent and can be exchanged between agents. A distinctive feature of a (business) service is that it has a goal to modify (and hence add value to) other resources. For example, the goal of the hairdressing service is to convert the customer’s hair. A (business) service does not specify how it is to be realized, i.e. how its goals are to be achieved. Instead, a service can be realized in many different ways.”</p>	<p>Service Owner Customer-Orientation Resource-Based Encapsulation</p>
BSD-11	<p>“Presenting business logic of a transaction or a business entity. The purpose of the service ... as business logic, or as specific- domain functions (e.g. a service for customer credit check).”</p>	<p>Functionality-/Capability-Orientation Customer-Orientation</p>
BSD-12	<p>“...the functional business part of these (business) services directly contributes to the creation of value in a networked value constellation according to the strategy defined by an organization.”</p>	<p>Customer-Orientation Value-Orientation Network-Orientation</p>
BSD-13	<p>“business services... created to realize and/or support the delivery of economic resources.”</p>	<p>Customer-Orientation Resource-Based Delivery Mechanism</p>
BSD-14	<p>“Business services are created to support the exchange of business values across a network of enterprises.”</p>	<p>Value-Orientation Network-Orientation</p>
BSD-15	<p>“In this paper, we use the term business service to refer to an autonomous transformational capability that is offered to and consumed by external or internal customers for their benefit.”</p>	<p>Customer-Orientation (Operant)Resource-Based Functionality-/Capability-Orientation Service Portfolio</p>
BSD-16	<p>“(1) Resource model (structure dimension): the resources required for the service to be provided correctly, comprising human resource capabilities, such as the definition of the skills required by the staff involved, information systems required, etc. (2) Process model (process dimension): describes how the outcomes of the service are achieved. (3) Product model (outcome dimension): describes what a service does and its outcomes (tangible and intangible).”</p>	<p>Resource-Based Functionality-/Capability-Orientation Delivery Mechanism Customer-Orientation</p>

Appendix C The Selected Studies Proposing SIMs

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Appendix D A Mapping between Business Service Design Concerns and SIMs

Table 17: A Mapping between Business Service Design Concerns and Business Service Identification Methods (SIMs)

SIMs	Business Service Design Concerns									
	DC-1: Service Owner	DC-2: Goal-Oriented	DC-3: Beneficiary-Oriented	DC-4: Value Oriented	DC-5: Capability-Encapsulation	DC-6: Resource-Encapsulation	DC-7: Formalization	DC-8: Delivery Mechanism	DC-9: Uniqueness	DC-10: Replicability
SIM-1	✓	✓	0	0	0	✓	✓	-	-	-
SIM-2	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-3	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-4	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-5	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-6	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-7	✓	0	0	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-8	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-9	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-10	✓	✓	0	0	0	✓	✓	-	-	-
SIM-11	✓	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-12	0	0	0	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-13	0	✓	0	0	0	✓	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-14	0	0	0	-	✓	-	✓	-	✓	✓
SIM-15	0	✓	0	0	0	✓	0	-	-	-
SIM-16	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-17	0	0	0	0	✓	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-18	✓	✓	0	0	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
SIM-19	-	-	-	-	0	-	✓	-	✓	✓
SIM-20	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-21	0	✓	0	0	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
SIM-22	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-23	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-24	✓	✓	0	0	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
SIM-25	-	0	-	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-
SIM-26	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-27	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-28	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-29	0	✓	0	0	0	✓	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-30	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-31	✓	✓	0	0	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
SIM-32	✓	0	0	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-33	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-34	✓	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-35	-	-	-	-	0	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-36	-	0	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-37	0	✓	0	0	0	✓	0	-	-	-
SIM-38	-	0	-	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-
SIM-39	0	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-
SIM-40	0	✓	0	0	0	✓	0	-	-	-
SIM-41	0	✓	0	✓	0	✓	✓	✓	-	-
SIM-42	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-43	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-44	✓	0	✓	-	0	-	✓	-	-	-
SIM-45	-	0	0	✓	0	✓	✓	✓	0	0
SIM-46	-	0	0	0	0	0	✓	✓	✓	✓
SIM-47	0	0	✓	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-

Legend: ✓ = Fully Addressed, 0 = Partially Addressed, - = Not Addressed